

Australian Citizen Science Association

Annual Report
2022 - 2023

Acknowledgement of Country

The Australian Citizen Science Association acknowledges the Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples of this nation. We pay our respects to ancestors and Elders, past and present, and recognise their unique cultural and spiritual relationships to the land, waters, and seas, as well as their rich contribution to society and citizen science.

Table of Contents

The Australian Citizen Science Association Annual Report 2022-2023 is published by the Australian Citizen Science Association Inc. (ACSA).

© Australian Citizen Science Association 2023

Cover image: Orchid discovery walk participants in Eurobodalla Regional Botanic Garden. Photo courtesy of Annie Lane.

Compiled by Jessie Oliver

Cite as: Australian Citizen Science Association. (2023). Australian Citizen Science Association Annual Report 2022-2023.

[10.5281/zenodo.10237787](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10237787)

Chair's Report	pg 03
About Us	pg 05
Our Achievements	pg 9
Chapter Triumphs	pg 15
Treasurer's Report	pg23
Acknowledgements & Thanks	pg 28
Appendix A. Governance	pg 32
Appendix B. Financial Statements	pg30

Chair's Report

Citizen science continues to flourish. Projects are increasing in number, diversity and complexity, government policies and strategies are recognising the value of citizen science, the community is more engaged than ever before, and stronger connections are being made across disciplines and organisations. In the past year, some notable examples of greater integration of citizen science into policy and research at a national level include The Threatened Species Action Plan and The State of the Environment Report. State Governments too are investing in citizen science. ACSA assisted the South Australia Department for Environment and Water in developing its citizen science strategy in consultation with the citizen science community in South Australia.

ACSA participated in consultations on revising Australia's National Research and Science Priorities, advocating for the critical role communities can play in addressing the significant environmental and social challenges we face as a country.

Despite the increasing recognition that citizen science provides a means to engage and educate, increase research capacity, open science to society and improve health and well-being, investment generally continues to lag. ACSA will continue to advocate for financial investment in citizen science to provide the leadership and supporting structures to enable citizen science to reach its enormous potential.

Developing new and strengthening existing partnerships to advance citizen science is another of ACSA's priorities. By way of example, over the past year, we entered into an agreement with the National Landcare Network to pursue opportunities to work together for the betterment of the environment and community. Environmentally focused citizen science and Landcare share commonalities in their focus on environmental stewardship, community engagement, and collaborative efforts to address environmental challenges.

At an international level, our tireless ACSA Citizen Science Global Partnerships (CSGP) liaison Libby Hepburn represents the Australian Citizen Science community as deputy chair of the CSGP Board and leader of action committees. A major focus of CSGP at present is the implementation of UNESCO's Recommendation on Open Science. ACSA is also now an affiliate of the Australian Open Science Network, which advocates for open science in Australia and explores ways to advance open science initiatives.

At a project level, ACSA hosted a total of five bioblitzes on behalf of the Minderoo Foundation in Perth, Melbourne and Sydney. To objective was to connect participants with nature and introduce them to the wonderful world of citizen science. Our delivery partners were Bamford Consulting Ecologists in Sydney, Port Phillip Ecocentre in Melbourne, and the University of NSW in Sydney.

*Orchid discovery walk participants in Eurobodalla Regional Botanic Garden.
Photo courtesy of Annie Lane.*

In terms of governance and engagement, the management committee reviewed and refreshed our ACSA's strategic plan, moved to a more efficient membership management system, awarded another two SEED grants, and continued to pepper our social media platforms to promote the wonderful projects and engagement opportunities provided by our members.

The hard work and support of many make the ACSA community! Many people make ACSA possible. A huge thank you to ACSA staff Jessie and Lisa, for going above and beyond to keep the organisation running, strengthening our administration, and governance systems and providing timely and informed responses to the increasing number of inquiries we receive. Thank you to members of the ACSA Management Committee and broader volunteers for providing your time, effort, and expertise towards strengthening our national peak body and promoting citizen science in your networks. Last but not least, thank you dear members for your commitment to ACSA and to citizen science. We could not exist without you.

Annie Lane
ACSA Chair

About Us

The Australian Citizen Science Association (ACSA) is the peak body for citizen science in Australia. ACSA was first conceived in 2014 when a large number of dedicated volunteers came together to discuss how to increase awareness and support of Australian citizen science both nationally and globally. The Association describes citizen science as a form of science involving public participation and collaboration in scientific inquiries with the aim to increase scientific knowledge.

Our Mission

A community that supports, informs, and develops citizen science.

Our Vision

To advance citizen science through the sharing of knowledge, collaboration, capacity building and advocacy.

Our Goals

Participation: Encourage and promote broad and meaningful participation in citizen science.

Partnerships: Facilitate inclusive and collaborative partnerships.

Practice: Support the development of tools and resources that further best practices.

Impact: Ensure the value and impact of citizen science and its outputs are

Organisation: Establish ACSA as an effective, trusted and well-recognised organisation and hub for citizen science in Australia.

Our People

During the reporting period, the ACSA Management Committee included four office bearers, two to four general members, and a representative from the University of Sydney as the ACSA host institution. Regional Chapter Chairs were also nominated to the Management Committee near the end of the financial year. The ACSA Management Committee was supported by our ACSA Citizen Science Global Partnership Liaison (CSGP), a Social Media Moderator, and a patron. The day-to-day operations of ACSA were conducted by part-time staff, including an Executive Officer and an Executive Support Officer, as well as a National Coordinator during a handover period. Once the Vice Chair's term ended, in 2022, she remained our public officer with Access Canberra.

Patron

Hugh Possingham
Patron
Full financial year

Annie Lane
Chair
Full financial year

Stephanie von Gavel
Vice Chair (VC)
Term ended
21 Nov 2022

Steve Turton
General Member to
VC / Chap Chair - QLD
Changed role on
21 Nov 2022 / Term
began 07 Oct 2022

Management Committee

Management Committee continued

Peter Runcie
Treasurer
Term ended
21 Nov 2022

Darryl Ebenezer
General Member to
Treasurer
Changed role on
21 Nov 2022

Bill Flynn
Secretary
Term ended
21 Nov 2022

Mary-Lou Gittins
Secretary
Term began
21 Nov 2022

Management Committee continued

Leigh Stitz
General Member
Term ended
21 Nov 2022

James Chong
General Member
Resigned 07 Jun 2023

Jock Mackenzie
General Member
Full financial year

Hannah Zurcher
General Member
Term began
21 Nov 2022

Kathryn Willis
General Member
Term began
21 Nov 2022

**Robbi Luscombe-
Newman**
General Member
Term began
21 Nov 2022

Louise Morris
General Member
Resigned 07 Jun 2023

Alice Motion
Host Institution
Representative
Full financial year

Regional Chapter Chairs

Alex Chapman
Chapter Chair for
Western Australia
Appointed to MC
07 Jun 2023

Patrick Bonney
Chapter Chair for
Victoria
Appointed to MC
07 Jun 2023

Sylvia Clarke
Chapter Chair for
South Australia
Appointed to MC
07 Jun 2023

Janine Bedros
Chapter Chair for
Queensland
Resigned 07 Oct 2022
Replaced by
Steve Turton Dec 2022

Employees

Amy Slocombe
National Coordinator
Resigned 29 Jul 2022

Jessie Oliver
International Liaison
to Executive Officer
Changed role on
25 Jul 2022

Lisa Evans
General Member to
Executive Support
Officer
Changed role on
25 Jul 2022

National Volunteers

Michelle Neil
Social Media
Moderator
Full financial year

Libby Hepburn
Citizen Science Global
Partnership
Full financial year

CITIZEN SCIENCE WITH ACSA

The Australian Citizen Science Association is a vibrant and growing community of citizen science professionals and enthusiasts. ACSA membership is open to anyone with an interest in citizen science. As an ACSA member, you'll be able to share ideas, pose questions, collaborate on projects, attend networking events and connect with people working, volunteering or fascinated in citizen science.

*Participants of the 1 Million Turtles Community Conservation Program burying chicken eggs at Big Bend, South Australia, for the National Nest Predation Survey.
Photo courtesy of Sylvia Clarke.*

Our Achievements

ACSA exists to represent citizen science at local, national, and international levels, as well as to actively advocate for the inclusion of citizen science in policy and practice. The ACSA operational objectives are to:

- ✿ Raise the profile of citizen science and ACSA through advocacy and outreach
- ✿ Deliver value for members
- ✿ Be financially secure to allow us to conduct impactful work
- ✿ Apply good governance practices to ensure we are working effectively and transparently

ACSA leadership undertook a variety of advocacy, consultation, liaison, and partnership activities to grow and strengthen citizen science. Following our [3-year ACSA strategic plan](#), we continued to grow citizen science diverse actions relating to participation, partnerships, practice, impact, and organisation. In the 2022-2023 financial year, we achieved goals in each area, and the examples featured below highlight our efforts to grow and support our members.

Participation

One of our biggest endeavours this year was facilitating a series of five bioblitzes. Each introduced volunteers from the Insurance Australia Group (IAG) to citizen science and the process of collecting and sharing plant, animal, and fungi observation. The [Australian Resilience Corps](#) supported the endeavour with an interest in fostering cooperative learning about nature to improve community resilience, disaster preparedness, and a sustainable future.

In November 2022, ACSA delivered:

- two events at the La Perouse area of southeastern Sydney,
- two events at St Kilda West Beach, Melbourne, and
- one event at Whiteman Park, Perth.

The effort was coordinated by Annie Lane, with facilitation support from regional Chapters and local biodiversity experts. What a success with 140 participants submitting nearly 1,400 records of over 380 species!

Bioblitz participants at La Perouse. Photos courtesy of Australian Resilience Corps

Participation continued

Additionally, we continued to grow our communication with members. Michelle Neil continued delivering social media posts. She keeps [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), [Instagram](#), [LinkedIn](#), and [YouTube](#) lively, despite unprecedented platform changes this year.

Join the conversation via our social media

For example, during global Citizen Science Month in April, Michelle joined forces with friends from SciStarter to co-lead an online citizen science “Twitter Conference” from the [@CitSciTC](#) Twitter account. People from Oceania, Asia, Africa, Europe and the Americas tweeted on April 1 at 12:01 PM from respective time zones. Collectively, the over 200 tweets gained 128,833 impressions, which can be viewed via [#CitSciTC](#).

More broadly, we kept our citizen science community informed through four issues of our national newsletter, masterfully pulled together by Lisa Evans. Three chapters sent out regionally-focused updates as well.

Our ACSA Chapters collectively offered our members and new audiences diverse opportunities to engage with citizen science (see the Chapter Triumphs section). During this financial year, our active Chapters were in South Australia (ACSA-SA), Victoria (ACSA-VIC), Western Australia (ACSA-WA), and Queensland (ACSA-QLD). With an eye to the future, we look to continue growing these chapters, reinvigorate the Australian Capital Territory (ACT) Chapter, and launch Chapters in New South Wales (NSW), Northern Territory (NT), and Tasmania (TAS).

Davina Paterson, the Cooloola Entomology Leader and Bugs Ed. presenter at the Cooloola Bioblitz 2022. Photo courtesy of Majenta Lehr-Reid.

Partnerships

This year, several new partnerships emerged. We are also delighted that the South Australia Chapter of ACSA initiated a partnership with COSMOS Science Magazine to feature citizen science stories, helping us to reach an entirely new audience. We were also thrilled to share that earlier this year we have teamed up with [National Landcare Network](#) as two peak bodies dedicated to supporting people understand our natural world and ensuring a sustainable future.

Several of our past partners extended citizen science engagements in new ways as well. The Australian Citizen Science Association is proud to partner with the Australian Academy of Science's Theo Murphy Initiative (Australia). ACSA team members, Jenn Loader and Alice Motion, played a pivotal role in forging the partnership. This collaboration will support three projects led by early- and mid-career researchers (EMCRs) investigating citizen science. More broadly, our past partnership with the Minderoo Foundation also evolved into ACSA facilitating the Australian Resilience Corp bioblitzes for IAG volunteers. We look forward to seeing how such cooperative endeavours continue to grow.

Several of our partnerships established in previous years have continued and strengthened. The University of Sydney continues to serve as the ACSA institutional host. We maintain the

appropriate and current insurance policies with the generous support of Queensland Water and Land Carers. The Australian Museum continues to provide invaluable logistical support. The Atlas of Living Australia continued maintaining the Australian Citizen Science Project Finder.

Additionally, we continue to progress shared goals with sister associations in Europe, the United States, Asia, and Africa as opportunities arise (see our [Memorandum of Understanding](#); e.g. Katherine Willis is supporting the planning of the 2024 ECSA conference). Libby Hepburn has also been instrumental in liaising with ACSA, the Citizen Science Global Partnership, Open Access Australasia, and the Australian Open Science Network to advance the implementation of the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#).

UNESCO Recommendation Cover

Practice

Several groups teamed up with ACSA to offer our members training opportunities. In July 2022, a free webinar on [Drones for Mapping Ecosystems](#), followed by a training course, with Dr Karen Joyce co-founder GeoNadir. In August, as part of National Science Week, Libby Hepburn and Michelle Neil hosted a [Bioblitz Symposium 2022](#) webinar, with presenters Michelle Nei, Larissa Braz Sousa, Thomas Mesaglio, Suvarna Parbhoo Mohan and Casey Kirchhoff. In September, Geetha Ortac kicked off a four-week course on the fundamentals of evaluation in citizen science. Such activities provided our members with rich learning opportunities.

This year, we supported the practice of citizen science through several activities. In September 2022, we gave back to our community by awarding two ACSA Seed Grants of \$1,000 each. Dr Larissa Braz Souza was awarded a grant to cover open-access fees for

publishing a scholarly paper about the [Great Southern Bioblitz](#). Dr Judy Friedlander was awarded the second grant to support the [National Schools B&B BioBlitz](#) during National Biodiversity Month.

Past and current ACSA leaders were invited to co-author two publications this year as well. One book chapter explores [Advancing the Productivity of Science with Citizen Science and Artificial Intelligence](#) as part of an open-access book released by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). Another is an article titled [Exploring How Citizen Science Projects Measuring Beach Plastic Debris Can Support UN Sustainable Development Goals](#), in the open-access journal [Citizen Science: Theory & Practice](#). We contributed to such work with the dual ambitions to reach new audiences and support the practice of citizen science.

Grant recipients Larissa Braz Souza (left) and Judy Friedlander (right)

Impact

This year, our impact often included advocacy through diverse forms of communication. Researchers asked us to be participants in their scholarly endeavours. We received several requests to present citizen science to new groups. ACSA leaders were increasingly invited to the table of local, state, national, and international meetings. We drafted several policy submissions featuring citizen science and best practices. The demand for such engagement and advocacy endeavours is only expected to increase. Procuring resources required to support us in meeting the demand will be essential.

Organisation

We have continued to grow our consulting activities. This year, we wrapped up our consulting with the Natural Resource Commission. The Minderoo Foundation partnered with us to deliver bioblitzes as part of the Australian Resilience Corps initiative. Additionally, the South Australia Department for Environment and Water engaged us to review their citizen science strategy. Such endeavours simultaneously advance our financial sustainability and participation goals.

Participants taking part in a Mangrove Watch survey on Clyde River Batemans Bay. Photo courtesy of Annie Lane.

Chapter Triumphs

Chapter Management Leaders

Sylvia Clarke
Chapter Chair
Full financial year

Katie Irvine
Chapter Vice Chair
Full financial year

Isabella Wilson
Chapter Secretary &
Newsletter Editor
Full financial year

Tahlia Perry
Chapter Public
Relations
Full financial year

SA At a Glance

6 **chapter newsletter issues** with growth of 90 to 213 subscribers

6 chapter meetings

1 new partnership forged

~24 public inquiry responses

4 chapter social catch-ups at the pub

2 sets of awards guidelines developed cooperatively

2 groups of external meetings and events attended

1 workshop presentation

1 consultation to collaboratively design bioblitz with Ferox australis

1 citizen science strategy consultation

Chapter Brief by Sylvia Clarke, Katie Irvine, & Isabella Wilson

It has been a really busy year with a lot of advocacy work undertaken with the Department for Environment and Water's election promise of a Citizen Science Fund taking shape. It was great to see the SA Citizen Science Awards reinstated in 2023 in collaboration with Inspiring South Australia and with support from SA Government Department of Environment and Water (DEW).

SA Citizen Science Awards during National Science Week. Photographed left to right: Amy Lee, Jasmin Packer, Wendy Stubbs, Sylvia Clarke, and Isabella Wilson. Photo courtesy of [Catherine Leo Photography](#).

The South Australia Chapter of ACSA (ACSA-SA) being involved in the SA Government Department for Environment and Water (DEW) citizen science grants enabled us to work together with the state government to ensure that the grants serve the citizen science community. Small grants have been awarded. The expression of interest round for the large grants of up to \$1.45M has recently closed. Visit the [DEW Environmental Citizen Science grants](#) webpage for details.

Participants at the Bremer Waterbug Bioblitz 2022. Photo courtesy of Andy Rasheed.

This year the South Australian Science Teachers Association (SASTA) approached the ACSA-SA Chapter to help develop a citizen science category for the Oliphant Science Awards in partnership with the SA State Government Department for Education. These awards are highly respected and have a very high engagement rate with primary and high schools across all sectors. It is very exciting to see citizen science now included in the awards to raise awareness, inspire, and educate young people about citizen science. The ACSA-SA Chapter also provided judging for the citizen science categories and we were pleased to see students' enthusiasm and efforts.

The ACSA-SA Chapter performs an important role as a community of practice for the state's active and interested practitioners drawing from members' expertise when people who are starting new projects call in/attend our meetings. Read about two examples on the next page.

Example 1: Manuel Esperon-Rodriguez from Australian Urban Trees

The Australian Urban Tree App highlighted the utility of citizen science in recording instances of tree planting failures - data that is typically poorly collected.

The ACSA SA Chapter community members discussed how citizen science can be integrated into this project, considering advantages, limitations, and future opportunities. Exploring this also led to broader discussions on topics such as the importance of data ownership for participants in fostering long-term participation (eg people adopting a tree or planting area to monitor over time), gamification, and involving local councils.

Preparation of soil of the Pakapakanthi (Victoria Park) Miyawaki pocket forest, as part of the citizen science program in conjunction with Earthwatch Australia. Photo courtesy of Doug McEvoy (see Example 2).

Example 2: Doug McEvoy from Green Pakapakanthi

In April 2023 a new community-led volunteer organisation, Green Pakapakanthi, was formed by the South East City Residents Association (SECRA) in collaboration with the City of Adelaide Council. Doug was interested in introducing citizen science to the Green Pakapakanthi project. Green Pakapakanthi aims to create more shade, improve biodiversity, and help “climate-proof” Pakapakanthi (Victoria Park).

ACSA-SA member Steve, who had previously done walks around the park/wetland, provided valuable advice based on his unique experience with both Pakapakanthi and citizen science. The ACSA-SA group also introduced citizen science methodologies and tools, such as BioBlitzes and iNaturalist, to Doug and his team.

The ACSA SA Chapter looks forward to engaging with more South Australians to develop, support and enhance citizen science activities in our state over the next year.

Chapter Management Leaders

Patrick Bonney
Chapter Chair
Full financial year

Ana Borda
Chapter Vice Chair
Full financial year

Kade Mills
Chapter Projects &
Partnerships
Full financial year

Elodie Camprasse
Chapter
Communications &
Social Media
Full financial year

Lynne Lucas
Chapter Projects &
Partnerships
Full financial year

Arjumand Khan
Chapter Projects &
Partnerships
Full financial year

Christina Renowden
Chapter
Communications &
Social Media
Resigned 31 May 2023

At a Glance

3 **chapter newsletter** issues with growth of 248 to 256 subscribers

~18 public inquiry responses

7 chapter meetings

14 meetings to advocate for citizen science

1 consultation to facilitate a bioblitz in collaboration

2 Chapter social media channels moderated (**Twitter** and **Facebook**)

1 citizen science engagement activity offered

1 presentation representing ACSA

1 citizen science strategy consultation

Chapter Brief by Patrick Bonney

The citizen science landscape in Victoria has continued to thrive, with diverse projects continuing to emerge to promote meaningful community engagement in scientific discovery. The Victorian chapter of the Australian Citizen Science Association (ACSA-VIC) has remained dedicated to fostering a strong citizen science community throughout Victoria through informal gatherings and partnership development.

During this financial year, we were pleased to welcome several new committee members who share a deep passion for citizen science. These individuals include Ann Borda (The University of Melbourne), Lynne Lucas (NDE, consultant), Arjumand Khan (STEM Catalyst), Christina Renowden

(Department of Environment, Energy, and Climate Action), and Elodie Camprasse (Deakin University). Additionally, Kade Mills from the Victorian National Parks Association, our former chair, continues to play an active role in the chapter.

Our first event for the year was held at the Royal Botanic Gardens in Melbourne and featured a free guided tour hosted by ClimateWatch, followed by a relaxed picnic in the gardens. Despite less-than-ideal weather conditions, we experienced a strong turnout for our first in-person event since the COVID-19 pandemic.

This year also marked a shift in focus for the chapter, with a greater emphasis on active involvement in

emerging projects to provide guidance on policy and project directions. For example, chapter members participated in the Citizen Science Collective, an advisory group brought together by the Department of Environment, Energy and Climate Action (DEECA, formerly DELWP) to contribute to the development of the Victorian Citizen Science Strategy. While the biodiversity-focused strategy remains in development, we have ensured that it incorporated the insights of citizen science practitioners from across the state, aligning it with on-ground issues and opportunities.

Additional activities included exploring opportunities with the City Nature Challenge Greater Melbourne from 28 April to 01 May 2023, led by Maroondah City Council and taking part in a research incubator workshop with the Health, Environment, Research and Action Research Incubator at The University of Melbourne. Our chapter also facilitated a bioblitz, as part of the ACSA consultation for the Minderoo Foundation.

*Minderoo Bioblitz participants in Victoria.
Photo courtesy of Patrick Bonney.*

Most recently, ACSA-VIC was actively engaged in the project steering committee for Agriculture Victoria's Biosecurity Quest, a project focused on raising awareness of biosecurity issues in Victoria and beyond.

While we have been proactive in supporting new and emerging projects, we have also maintained our commitment to long-standing citizen science initiatives in Victoria. This included representing ACSA in an online panel discussion celebrating 30 years of waterway citizen science in Victoria. A fantastic achievement for the WaterWatch Victoria program! You can watch the video titled The Past Present and Future of WaterWatch Panel Discussion on Youtube.

WaterWatch Victoria coordinators and volunteers. Photo courtesy of Jake Van Dam.

Looking ahead, we are focused on cultivating new relationships while strengthening existing connections between ACSA and the Victorian citizen science community. We have some exciting plans in the works and look forward to sharing the outcomes of these efforts through our social media channels and regular newsletter updates.

Australian Citizen Science Association | WA

Chapter Management Leaders

Alex Chapman
Chapter Chair
Full financial year

Marnie Giroud
Chapter Vice
Chair
Full financial year

Lisa Evans
Chapter General
Member
Full financial year

Tegan Douglas
Chapter General
Member
Full financial year

Claire Greenwell
Chapter General
Member
Full financial year

Kelly Sheldrick
Chapter General
Member
Full financial year

At a Glance

1 chapter forum with 12 speakers and ~50 participants

1 social media channel ([Facebook](#))

10 chapter meetings

~24 chapter inquiries per year

1 consultation to facilitate bioblitzes

Chapter Brief by Alex Chapman

ACSA-WA had a productive year in 2022-23, with several excellent engagement opportunities. The State chapter pledged to hold a major citizen science event in the year between the national conferences. As such, we organised a Citizen Science Forum in July 2022 focussed on the theme 'Pathways to Citizen Science'.

Alex kicking off the 2022 Pathways to Citizen Science forum in Perth. Photo courtesy of Samantha Brown.

<p>Dr Elizabeth Kington Chair, WA Malleefowl Recovery Group</p>					
<p>Cathy Levett Project Coordinator</p>					
<p>Dr Lisa Evans Executive Support Officer</p>					

An overview of the speakers and topics at the 2022 Citizen Science Forum. Photo courtesy of Alex Chapman.

This Forum highlighted practitioners across many domains, especially focussing on pathways to engaging in citizen science from a tertiary education perspective. Speakers from a number of WA universities and NGOs delivered exhilarating exposes on their innovative and engaging projects.

The Forum was held at the University of Western Australia on 20 August 2022 with the aforementioned 12 speakers and about 50 attendees and live-streamers giving a range of informative presentations. During the break, Deborah Bowie, from the University of Western Australia (UWA) and UWA students presented science posters.

The other major event in the last financial year was the corporate citizen science event on the 9th of November 2022 - the Perth Corporate Bioblitz at Whiteman Park, Perth. In total, 45 participants joined one of three different surveys during the morning and afternoon choosing between plants, insects and birds.

These surveys were led by subject experts and educators, walking at a leisurely pace allowing time to ask questions, share stories and record observations. These were captured using the iNaturalist app contributing data to the Atlas of Australia platform (see the [Perth Whiteman Park Bioblitz project on iNaturalist Australia](#)). These BioBlitzes were supported by the Australian Resilience Corps, and hosted by ACSA, for IAG's Resilience Day - NRMA Insurance's National Day of Help.

Local advocacy continued as well. Chapter member of ACSA-WA, Dr Tegan Douglas, for example, presented Citizen Science in WA to the Lesmurdie branch of the University of the Third Age (U3A) on 6 June 2022. True to the Noongar season of Makuru, the weather was cold and blustery, but not even hail was enough to stop this group of curious minds and life-long learners from gathering at Falls Farm in Lesmurdie to hear about how easy it is to get involved with citizen science.

*Tegan Douglas (right) and Julie Holland (left) at the Lesmurdie branch of the University of the Third Age.
Photo courtesy of Heidi Pember.*

Australian Citizen Science Association | QLD

Chapter Management Leaders

Janine Bedros
Chapter Chair
Resigned 07 Oct 2022

Steve Turton
Chapter Chair
Term began
07 Oct 2022

Darryl Ebenezer
Chapter Vice Chair
Full financial year

Luise Manning
Chapter Secretary
Resigned 07 Oct 2022

Melissa Dobbins
Chapter General
Member
Full financial year

Sandra Tuszynska
Chapter General
Member
18 Nov 2023

Jennifer Seevinck
Chapter General
Member
Resigned 07 Oct 2022

At a Glance

2 **Chapter newsletter issues** with 406 subscribers

~18 public inquiry responses

1 conference partnership

5 webinars

5 chapter meetings

20 conference planning meetings

Chapter Brief by Steve Turton, Jessie Oliver, and Janine Bedros

In the first half of the financial year, the QLD Chapter delivered several webinars. Topics covered were diverse, from mangroves in education to the sounds of frogs. Two such talks were recorded and can be found on the ACSA YouTube channel:

- On 25 August 2022, the webinar **Whale Research with Dr Wally Franklin** highlighted how photographs of whales can support the research of individuals, and how platforms such as Happy Whale and Fluke Book can support such endeavours.
- On 26 October 2022, the webinar **FrogID with Nadiah Roslan** featured how the submission of frog calls from across Australia via the FrogID application is informing frog research and conservation.

Those signed up for the ACSA-QLD newsletter also got two jam-packed issues written by Luise Manning.

Top: Luise Manning (left) and Dr Oliver Knox (right) at the National Landcare Conference in Sydney in November 2022. Bottom: Dr Knox shows what happens to undies when buried in soil as part of the Soil Your Undies project.

Janine Bedros, Luise Manning, Sandra Tuszynska, and Jennifer Seevinck each stepped down within the year, and we would like to thank them for their dedication to citizen science and growing the QLD chapter.

This year ushered in Steve Turton as the new Chapter Chair, with a new meeting structure, where two people for each meeting presented 10 slides in 10 minutes. This gave attendees an introduction to a wide range of citizen science topics, from earthquake detection to social media conferencing.

In the second half of the financial year, the ACSA Queensland Chapter members shifted focus towards planning an Australian Citizen Science Conference for November 2023. First, a relationship with the Sunshine Coast University as the host of the conference. Then, a conference committee, with many QLD residents, was formed, for planning to move full steam ahead.

Dion Dior (Artist and Nature Journaling Educator), Wendy Major (Nature Journaling participant), and Joel Fostin (Pandanus expert) at the Cooloola Bioblitz 2022 Nature Journaling Art Program. Photo courtesy of Joolie Gibbs.

Treasurer's Report

Financial Position

At the end of the 2023 financial year, 30 June 2023, ACSA held \$133,095 in net assets (i.e. assets minus liabilities). Assets primarily consist of \$135,862 in cash and \$1,346 in receivables owing.

Financial Performance

Obtaining core funding to meet the aspirations of the ACSA committee, deliver on our strategic plan and continue to provide services to members continues to be a challenge. Many people and organisations talk about the importance of citizen science and the valuable investment of tens of thousands of volunteers. This has not yet been translated into resources. The committee and staff continue to explore opportunities for funding. I look forward to being able to report more positively next year. At the end of the 2023 financial year, we reported a loss of \$50,060. This was due to our investment in staff to assist in the operations of ACSA and progressing our strategic plan. We anticipate that in the coming year, we will increase our income.

It is a pleasure to report that income from membership fees and donations totalled \$20,676 by the end of the 2023 financial year (i.e. a decrease of only \$179 from 2022).

The Future

For the 2023-2024 financial year, we will continue to focus on obtaining income to support the ongoing sustainability of the organisation, and to add value to our members and the Australian citizen science community more broadly. On behalf of the ACSA Management Committee, I extend our gratitude to our members, funding bodies, partners, and staff for their essential financial and logistical support. We look forward to positive responses to grant submissions that will be decided in late 2023.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Darryl Ebenezer'.

**Darryl
Ebenezer**
ACSA Treasurer

Acknowledgements & Thanks

Partners

Organisational Members

Volunteers and Supporters

Thank you to our volunteers, members, and broader supporters! Whether volunteering time and efforts, purchasing a membership, or providing other forms of support, we are very appreciative. We recognise that our work would not be possible without your generosity.

Cedric Varcoe monitoring turtles with the Ngarrindjeri Aboriginal Corporation as part of the 1 Million Turtles Community Conservation Program in collaboration with the Department for Environment and Water and The University of Adelaide. Photo courtesy of Scotte Wedderburn, The University of Adelaide.

Volunteers at a nest survey with Professor Mike Thompson as part of the 1 Million Turtles Community Conservation Program in February 2023. Photo courtesy of Sylvia Clarke.

Australian Citizen Science Association

Contact Us

+61 (0)422 559 778

executiveofficer@citizenscience.org.au

citizenscience.org.au

ACSA Inc, PO Box 851 Maleny Qld 4552

Follow Us

www.facebook.com/AustralianCitizenScienceAssociation

www.linkedin.com/groups/6721312

www.twitter.com/CitSciOZ

www.instagram.com/citsci_oz

www.youtube.com/c/AustralianCitizenScienceAssociation

Appendix A. Governance

Our Organisation

The Australian Citizen Science Association was registered as an incorporated association (Registration No. A 05747) via the Registrar-General's Office in the Australian Capital Territory in June 2016 and began following regulations upheld by Access Canberra. A year later, the Australian Citizen Science Association Incorporated (ACSA) registered to be an Australian Registered Body (ARB No. 618 948 271) with the Australian Securities & Investment Commission (ASIC), allowing the Association to conduct business throughout all states and territories within Australia. In July 2018, ACSA was certified as a registered small charity with the Australian Charities and Not-for-profits Commission (ACNC).

The Association is governed by a constitution that sets out the high-level objectives, powers, and administrative arrangements, in accordance with the Associations Incorporation Act 1991 and regulations set by the above-mentioned bodies.

Our Management Committee

The Association is led by a volunteer Management Committee (MC). The MC consists of a Chair, Vice Chair, Secretary, and Treasurer, as well as at least two general members. Members of the MC are elected by ACSA members and endorsed at the Annual

General Meeting for a two-year term, and MC members can opt to nominate for additional terms. Additionally, the MC includes a representative from the host organisation of ACSA, which is currently the University of Sydney. Collectively, ACSA Management Committee members have knowledge or experience in areas such as citizen science, science, business, finance, stakeholder engagement, and fundraising.

Our Sub-Committees

Sub-committees are formed to advance the implementation of the ACSA strategic plan. These sub-committees provide advice and make recommendations to the MC. Membership of sub-committees consists of MC members, broader volunteers, and staff with expertise, interest, and sometimes responsibilities in the subject area. During 2022-2023, three sub-committees met regularly:

- Governance and Advocacy;
- Finance; and
- Membership, Engagement and Communications.

An ACSA Conference committee was also formed to organise our 2023 conference.

Our Broader Leadership Roles

ACSA also has a number of individual members who act on behalf of ACSA in

specific volunteer roles created to advance the organisational mission. For instance, the ACSA MC has appointed the specialist roles of ACSA Patron, ACSA Social Media Moderator, ACSA Citizen Science Global Partnership (CSGP) Liaison.

Our State and Territory Chapters

ACSA Regional Chapters promote ACSA and citizen science through diverse community engagement activities. Chapter Chairs attend Management Committee meetings to relay national and chapter information back and forth. Chapters follow ACSA Chapter Protocols set forth by the MC. However, chapters are otherwise self-organised and make their own governance and operational arrangements.

Our Employees

During the 2022-2023 financial year ACSA had a part-time Executive Officer and a part-time Executive Support Officer. Together, they support the MC by carrying out operational activities. The Association also engaged contractors on an as-needed basis to support the organisation and implementation of large-scale events, ACSA consulting business, and other operational activities.

Our Consulting

In addition to membership subscriptions, revenue can be generated through ACSA Consulting.

Proceeds of our consulting services work are used to advance citizen science in Australia. ACSA Consulting offers a wide range of services. A few examples of what we can offer include:

- Creating citizen science strategies
- Developing citizen science implementation plans
- Designing citizen science programs, projects, or technologies
- Devising citizen science management and evaluation techniques
- Recommending citizen science best practice approaches
- Facilitating workshops and events
- Delivering keynote addresses

Our Membership Structure

In the 2017-2018 financial year, a financial membership structure was introduced for ACSA, as a step towards ensuring the Association became a self-sustaining organisation.

Membership types and fees per annum during the 2022-2023 financial year were:

- **Concession:** a subscription for a member with a student, senior (60+), pensioner, or veteran concession: \$40
- **Individual:** a subscription for a member at the full rate: \$80
- **Organisation - Small:** a subscription for up to 2 members from an organisation: \$150
- **Organisation - Medium:** a subscription for up to 5 members from an organisation: \$350
- **Organisation - Large:** a subscription for 6 to 15 members from an organisation: \$860

During the 2022-2023 financial year, we made the transition from a membership renewal cycle based on the anniversary of an individual’s membership to a cycle of a fixed calendar date for all members. All memberships are now set to renew annually, on July 1st to align with the start of each financial year. New members who join (or expired members who rejoin) at other times pay prorated membership dues based on the month their membership commences. All prices above are GST-inclusive.

Appendix B. Financial Statements

AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

**FINANCIAL REPORT
FOR THE YEAR ENDED
30 JUNE 2023**

**Liability limited by a scheme approved under
Professional Standards Legislation**

AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

CONTENTS

Income and Expenditure Statement	1
Balance Sheet	4
Cash Flow Statement - Direct Method	5
Notes to the Financial Statements	6
Statement by Members of the Committee	10
Compilation Report	11

**INCOME AND EXPENDITURE STATEMENT
FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2023**

	2023	2022
	\$	\$
<u>INCOME</u>		
SALES		
Membership Fees, Donations	20,676	20,855
Consulting Services	72,005	65,060
Ticket Sales (Events)	-	-
Merchandise	243	776
Total Sales	92,924	86,691
GRANT OPERATING		
Government Grant	-	-
JobSaver Subsidy	-	18,804
Other Grants	-	50,500
Total Grants Operating	-	69,304
DONATIONS & SPONSORSHIP		
Sponsorship	-	3,000
Conference Income	-	23,183
Total Donations & Sponsorship	-	26,183
OTHER INCOME		
Interest Received	170	138
Workcover Refund	195	-
Stripe Fees	25	-
Total Other Income	390	138
TOTAL INCOME	93,314	182,316

The accompanying notes form part of these financial statements.
These statements should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

**INCOME AND EXPENDITURE STATEMENT
FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2023**

	2023	2022
	\$	\$
<u>EXPENDITURE</u>		
Accounting & Bookkeeping	1,868	753
Chapter Expenses	362	1,345
Community and Social Gifting	20,000	1,164
Computer Equipment	2,055	
Consultants Fees	35,501	49,352
Event Catering	-	360
Event Registration	-	1,227
Honorarium Payments	1,000	-
Printing, Stationery & Postage	22	422
Professional Fees	11,856	-
Promotional Merchandise and Collateral	-	2,990
Provision for Holiday Pay	1,881	
Subscriptions	3,002	1,851
Superannuation Contributions	3,611	3,575
SupporterHub / Stripe Fees	303	296
Travelling Expenses	653	3,859
Wages	36,281	34,266
Wages - International	24,000	-
Website Domain and Plug in Expenses	106	27
Website Hosting	782	242
Workcare Insurance	91	421
TOTAL EXPENDITURE	143,374	102,150
(Loss) Profit before income tax	(50,060)	80,166

The accompanying notes form part of these financial statements.
These statements should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

Page 2

**INCOME AND EXPENDITURE STATEMENT
FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2023**

	2023	2022
	\$	\$
(Loss) Profit for the year	(50,060)	80,166
Retained earnings at the beginning of the financial year	183,155	102,988
Retained earnings at the end of the financial year	133,095	183,154

The accompanying notes form part of these financial statements.
These statements should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

Page 3

**BALANCE SHEET
AS AT 30 JUNE 2023**

	Note	2023 \$	2022 \$
ASSETS			
CURRENT ASSETS			
Cash and cash equivalents	3	135,862	140,702
Trade and other receivables	4	1,346	47,234
TOTAL CURRENT ASSETS		<u>137,208</u>	<u>187,936</u>
NON-CURRENT ASSETS			
Property, plant and equipment	5	-	2,055
TOTAL NON-CURRENT ASSETS		<u>-</u>	<u>2,055</u>
TOTAL ASSETS		<u>137,208</u>	<u>189,991</u>
LIABILITIES			
CURRENT LIABILITIES			
Trade and other payables	6	3,389	5,847
Superannuation Payable		724	990
TOTAL CURRENT LIABILITIES		<u>4,113</u>	<u>6,837</u>
TOTAL LIABILITIES		<u>4,113</u>	<u>6,837</u>
NET ASSETS		<u>133,095</u>	<u>183,154</u>
MEMBERS' FUNDS			
Capital Reserve	7	133,095	183,154
TOTAL MEMBERS' FUNDS		<u>133,095</u>	<u>183,154</u>

The accompanying notes form part of these financial statements.
These statements should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

**CASH FLOW STATEMENT – DIRECT METHOD
FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2023**

	2023	2022
	\$	\$
CASH FLOWS FROM OPERATING ACTIVITIES		
Receipts from customers	21,564	22,436
Payments to suppliers and employees	(63,892)	(37,840)
Cash Receipts from other operating activities	127,728	118,903
Cash Payments from other operating activities	(90,577)	(65,626)
Net cash provided by (used in) operating activities	<u>(5,177)</u>	<u>37,873</u>
CASH FLOWS FROM FINANCING ACTIVITIES		
Other Activities	337	(561)
Net cash provided by (used in) financing activities	<u>337</u>	<u>(561)</u>
Net increase (decrease) in cash held	(4,840)	37,312
Cash at beginning of financial year	140,702	103,390
Cash at end of financial year	<u>135,862</u>	<u>140,702</u>

The accompanying notes form part of these financial statements.
These statements should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

Page 5

NOTES TO THE FINANCIAL STATEMENTS FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2023

The financial statements cover Australian Citizen Science Association as an individual entity. Australian Citizen Science Association is a not for profit Association incorporated in ACT under the Associations Incorporation Act 1991.

The functional and presentation currency of Australian Citizen Science Association is Australian dollars.

Comparatives are consistent with prior years, unless otherwise stated.

1 Basis of Preparation

In the opinion of the Committee of Management, the Association is not a reporting entity since there are unlikely to exist users of the financial report who are not able to command the preparation of reports tailored so as to satisfy specifically all of their information needs. These special purpose financial statements have been prepared to meet the reporting requirements of the Act.

The financial statements have been prepared in accordance with the recognition and measurement requirements of the Australian Accounting Standards and Accounting Interpretations, and the disclosure requirements of AASB 101 Presentation of Financial Statements, AASB 107 Statement of Cash Flows, AASB 108 Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors and AASB 1054 Australian Additional Disclosures.

The financial statements have been prepared on an accruals basis and are based on historical costs modified, where applicable, by the measurement at fair value of selected non-current assets, financial assets and financial liabilities.

Significant accounting policies adopted in the preparation of these financial statements are presented below and are consistent with prior reporting periods unless otherwise stated.

The following significant accounting policies, which are consistent with the previous period unless stated otherwise, have been adopted in the preparation of this financial report.

2 Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Plant and Equipment

Each class of plant and equipment is carried at cost less, where applicable, any accumulated depreciation and impairment.

Plant and equipment is depreciated on a straight-line basis over the assets useful life to the Association, commencing when the asset is ready for use

These notes should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

Page 6

NOTES TO THE FINANCIAL STATEMENTS FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2023

Impairment of Non-Financial Assets

At the end of each reporting period the association determines whether there is evidence of an impairment indicator for non-financial assets.

Where this indicator exists and regardless for goodwill, indefinite life intangible assets and intangible assets not yet available for use, the recoverable amount of the asset is estimated.

Where assets do not operate independently of other assets, the recoverable amount of the relevant cash-generating unit (CGU) is estimated.

The recoverable amount of an asset or CGU is the higher of the fair value less costs of disposal and the value in use. Value in use is the present value of the future cash flows expected to be derived from an asset or cash-generating unit.

Where the recoverable amount is less than the carrying amount, an impairment loss is recognised in profit or loss.

Reversal indicators are considered in subsequent periods for all assets which have suffered an impairment loss, except for goodwill.

Income Tax

The association is a not-for-profit organisation and is exempt from income tax under section 50-45 of the Income Tax Assessment Act 1997.

Employee Benefits

Provision is made for the association's liability for employee benefits arising from services rendered by employees to the end of the reporting period. Employee benefits that are expected to be wholly settled within one year have been measured at the amounts expected to be paid when the liability is settled.

Employee benefits expected to be settled more than one year after the end of the reporting period have been measured at the present value of the estimated future cash outflows to be made for those benefits. In determining the liability, consideration is given to employee wage increases and the probability that the employee may satisfy vesting requirements. Changes in the measurement of the liability are recognised in profit or loss.

Cash and Cash Equivalents

Cash and cash equivalents comprises cash on hand, demand deposits and short term investments which are readily convertible to known amounts of cash and which are subject to an insignificant risk of change in value.

These notes should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

Page 7

NOTES TO THE FINANCIAL STATEMENTS FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2023

Revenue and Other Income

Revenue is recognised when the amount of the revenue can be measured reliably, it is probable that economic benefits associated with the transaction will flow to the association and specific criteria relating to the type of revenue as noted below, has been satisfied.

Revenue is measured at the fair value of the consideration received or receivable and is presented net of returns, discounts and rebates.

Sale of goods

Revenue from the sale of goods is recognised at the point of delivery as this corresponds to the transfer of significant risks and rewards of ownership of the goods and the cessation of all involvement in those goods.

Interest revenue

Interest revenue is recognised using the effective interest rate method.

Goods and Services Tax (GST)

Revenue, expenses and assets are recognised net of the amount of goods and services tax (GST), except where the amount of GST incurred is not recoverable from the Australian Taxation Office (ATO).

Receivables and payables are stated inclusive of GST.

Cash flows in the cash flow statement are included on a gross basis and the GST component of cash flows arising from investing or financing activities which is recoverable from, or payable to, the taxation authority is classified as operating cash flows.

These notes should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

Page 8

**NOTES TO THE FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2023**

	2023 \$	2022 \$
3 Cash and Cash Equivalents		
Community Access Account	135,549	140,702
Cash at Bank - Stripe	313	-
	<u>135,862</u>	<u>140,702</u>
4 Trade and Other Receivables		
Current		
Trade Debtors	510	47,234
Tax clearing account	836	-
	<u>1,346</u>	<u>47,234</u>
5 Property, plant and equipment		
Computer Equipment	-	2,055
Total Plant and Equipment	-	2,055
Total Property, Plant and Equipment	-	2,055
6 Accounts Payable and Other Payables		
Current		
PAYG Withholding Payable	1,508	906
Tax clearing account	-	4,941
Provision for Holiday Pay	1,881	-
	<u>3,389</u>	<u>5,847</u>
7 Retained Earnings		
Retained earnings at the beginning of the financial year	183,155	102,988
(Net loss) Net profit attributable to the association	<u>(50,060)</u>	<u>80,166</u>
Retained earnings at the end of the financial year	<u>133,095</u>	<u>183,154</u>

8 Statutory Information

The registered office of the association is:
c/o Faculty of Science, Partner Engagement and Outreach
Room 231, Level 2 Carslaw Building F07
University of Sydney
Sydney 2006, Australia

These notes should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

Page 9

AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

STATEMENT BY MEMBERS OF THE COMMITTEE

The committee has determined that the association is not a reporting entity and that this special purpose financial report should be prepared in accordance with the accounting policies outlined in Note 2 to the financial statements.

In the opinion of the committee the financial report :

1. Presents a true and fair view of the financial position of Australian Citizen Science Association as at 30 June 2023 and its performance for the year ended on that date.
2. At the date of this statement, there are reasonable grounds to believe that Australian Citizen Science Association will be able to pay its debts as and when they fall due.

This statement is made in accordance with a resolution of the Committee and is signed for and on behalf of the Committee by:

Chair:
Annette Lane

Dated: 9/11/2023

Treasurer:
Darryl Ebenezer

Dated: 6/11/2023

COMPILATION REPORT TO AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

We have compiled the accompanying special purpose financial statements of Australian Citizen Science Association which comprise the balance sheet as at 30 June 2023, profit and loss statement and cash flow statement for the year then ended, a summary of significant accounting policies and other explanatory notes. The specific purpose for which the special purpose financial statements have been prepared is set out in the notes to the accounts.

The responsibility of the committee of management

The Committee of Management of Australian Citizen Science Association is solely responsible for the information contained in the special purpose financial statements, the reliability, accuracy and completeness of the information and for the determination that the basis of accounting used is appropriate to meet their needs and for the purpose that the financial statements were prepared.

Our responsibility

On the basis of the information provided by the committee of management we have compiled the accompanying special purpose financial statements in accordance with the basis of accounting as described in the notes to the financial statements and APES 315: Compilation of Financial Information.

We have applied professional expertise in accounting and financial reporting to compile these financial statements in accordance with the basis of accounting described in the notes to the financial statements. We have complied with the relevant ethical requirements of APES 110 Code of Ethics for Professional Accountants.

Assurance Disclaimer

Since a compilation engagement is not an assurance engagement, we are not required to verify the reliability, accuracy or completeness of the information provided to us by management to compile these financial statements. Accordingly, we do not express an audit opinion or a review conclusion on these financial statements.

The special purpose financial statements were compiled exclusively for the benefit of the committee of management who are responsible for the reliability, accuracy and completeness of the information used to compile them. Accordingly, these special purpose financial statements may not be suitable for other purposes. We do not accept responsibility to any other person for the contents of the special purpose financial statements.

Name of Firm: J & M Accountants & Business Advisors
Certified Practising Accountants

Name of Partner:

Janine Brumhead

Address: Level 6, 34 Queen St MELBOURNE VIC 3000

Dated this 18th day of October 2023